

SURVEY ON DISTRIBUTED GENERATION BASED DIFFERENT MULTILEVEL DC-AC POWER INVERTER FOR HARMONIC REDUCTION

V. Meera

PG Scholar, Easa College of Engineering & Technology, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: V. Meera, "Survey on Distributed Generation Based Different Multilevel DC-AC Power Inverter for Harmonic Reduction", International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology, Page Number 89-92, Volume 1,

Issue 2, 2016.

Abstract:

Multilevel inverter has been under research and development for more than three decades and has found successful industrial application. Also, it has become the enabling power conversion technology for high voltage and high power applications in present power systems and large electric motor drives. The propagated energy source consists of solar cells, wind turbines, micro-turbines (natural gas), fuel cells and storage batteries and also connected to the low voltage distribution network through power electronics converters. Here, the fast response and autonomous control, the use of a multilevel converter to control the voltage and frequency output from renewable energy sources will provide significant advantages. It can be also control the real and reactive power flow from a utility connected renewable energy source. There are various control strategy used offer the possibility to inject electrical energy from the different renewable sources and on the other hand to reduce the harmonic distortion for AC load applications. The multilevel inverter is used to provide the improvement of performance including such as harmonic compensation, power factor correction, THD (total harmonic distortion), voltage and current balancing.

Key Words: Renewable Energy, Multilevel Inverter, Harmonic Suppression, Power Conversion & Pulse Width Modulation

1. Introduction:

Recently, the installations of more distributed generators (DG) in power distribution networks are encouraging the entry of power generation and energy storage at the distribution level. The different of MFI system configurations of DG systems are essential to future utility grids for the delivery of high-quality, reliable, and efficient electricity supply [1-3]. The main power is generated by different renewable energy sources for various operating conditions. The multilevel based pulse width modulation (PWM) inverter for grid connection employing PI controller to perform unity power factor and capability of grid connection with high efficiency [4]. The applications of multilevel converters consists of include such as industrial medium voltage motor drives, hybrid electric vehicles charge stations, renewable energy systems with utility interface, flexible AC transmission system (FACTS), subsea oil/gas, high voltage direct current (HVDC) and traction drive systems. The common multilevel converter topologies are consider as neutral point-clamped converter (NPC), flying capacitor converter (FC) and Cascade H-Bridge (CHB) have been developed for better medium and high power applications [5-6]. The power conversion interface is important to grid connected solar power generation systems because it converts the dc power generated by a solar cell array into ac power and feeds this ac power into the utility grid. An inverter is necessary in the power conversion interface to convert the dc power to ac power. Since the output voltage of a solar cell array is low, a dc-dc power converter is used in a small-capacity solar power generation system to boost the output voltage, so it can match the dc bus voltage of the inverter [7-8]. The power conversion efficiency of the power conversion interface is important to insure that there is no waste of the energy generated by the solar cell array. Conventional multilevel inverter topologies include the diode clamped, the flying-capacitor, and the cascade H-bridge types. Diode-clamped and flying capacitor multilevel inverters use capacitors to develop several voltage levels. But it is difficult to regulate the voltage of these capacitors. Since it is difficult to create an asymmetric voltage technology in both the diode-clamped and the flying capacitor topologies, the power circuit is complicated by the increase in the voltage levels that is necessary for a multilevel inverter [9-10]. For a single-phase seven-level inverter, 12 power electronic switches are required in both the diode-clamped and the flying-capacitor topologies. Asymmetric voltage technology is used in the cascade H-bridge multilevel inverter to allow more levels of output voltage, so the cascade H-bridge multilevel inverter is suitable for applications with increased voltage levels.

2. Renewable Energy Resources:

The distributed resource such as wind energy, solar PV panel and fuel cell connected via DC-DC converter for micro grid applications. The basic idea of this paper is to utilize the multi level inverter interfaced propagated generation to compensate multiple harmonic components and power factor correction.

2.1 Wind Turbine with PMSG System:

The growing interest in wind turbine applications and the fast development of power electronics is making the manufacturers to find the most suitable and low cost technologies to put in recent applications. A

wind turbine operates by extracting kinetic energy from the wind passing through its rotor. The power developed by a wind turbine is given by,

$$P = 1/2 C_p v V_w^3 A \tag{1}$$

Figure 1: Block Diagram of Wind Turbine Fed PMSG Configuration

Permanent magnet synchronous generator are becoming more popular over the induction machine in wind turbine applications, because of the increased power to volume ratio, high reliability, decreasing cost of magnets, increased efficiency and no need of external excitation, smaller in size and easy to control. Also, it having an efficient and a reliable control is very important to have a better understanding of the system. The PMSG with wind turbines circuit is shown below in figure 1.

2.2 PV with Multilevel System:

The simplest PV model can be considered as a diode. When exposed to light, the electrons and holes are separated when the photos energy is greater than the band gap energy. Under the influence of the electric field of the p-n junction diode, the electrons and holes flow through an external circuit. Finally, the light energy can be converted into the electrical energy. An important decision with the array was to decide to model it either with current or voltage as the output.

$$I = I_{PV,cell} - I_{0,cell} \left[\exp\left(\frac{qv}{aKT}\right) - 1 \right] I_d \tag{2}$$

Figure 2: Schematic Block diagram of PV with Multilevel Inverter

The PV system generates dc power determined mainly by the level of solar radiation. The output power is then converted to ac power for injection into the grid through a dc -dc boost converter and a dc-ac power inverter as shown in Fig.2.

2.3 Fuel Cell with Multilevel System:

The fuel cell is an electrochemical device that converts chemical energy form into electrical and thermal energies form. Fuel cells are starting to meet the power needs of a variety of applications. In this paper, a suitable SB-PWM (simple boost pulse width modulation) is implemented and generation potential of PEMFC (Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell) developed. The fuel cell with multilevel inverter topology is shown in figure 3.

$$V_{cell} = E_{thermo} - V_{act} - V_{ohmic} - V_{conc} \tag{3}$$

Figure 3: Schematic diagram of Fuel cell with MLI Topology

The PEM fuel cell with DC-DC power converter structure allows to avoiding non minimum phase property and output voltage is controlled directly, that simplifies the controller design. The above configuration can be achieving high-voltage converters with low-voltage devices. The major advantages of this topology consider as continuous input current, a large conversion ratio without extreme duty cycle and without transformer, which allow high switching frequency.

3. Configuration of Multilevel Inverter:

The multilevel voltage-source inverters are intensively studied for high-power applications and standard drives for medium-voltage industrial applications become available. In order to increase number of output voltage levels have the capability to synthesize waveforms with a better harmonic spectrum and to limit the motor winding insulation stress. Generally, the multilevel inverter is a power electronic system that synthesizes a sinusoidal voltage output from several DC sources. These DC sources can be wind energy, fuel cells, solar cells, ultra capacitors, etc. The main idea of multilevel inverters is to have a better sinusoidal voltage and current in the output by using switches in series.

Figure 4: Simple multilevel inverter topology

Since many switches are put in series the switching angles are important in the multilevel inverters because all of the switches should be switched in such a way that the output voltage and current has been low harmonic distortion. The output voltage is obtained by the sum of the voltage that is generated by each cell. The number of output voltage levels are $2n+1$, where n is the number of cells. The switching angles could be taken as in such a way condition, so that the total harmonic distortion is minimized.

Figure 5: Various level waveforms of multilevel inverter

The multilevel inverter concept does not depend upon the two levels (+ve & -ve) of AC signal. Increasing voltage levels are preferred to produces the smooth output waveform but with several levels based becomes need more switches as well as more complication, simplified multi level inverter and its various form of level waveforms of multilevel inverter are shown in figure. 4 & 5. Thus the MLI techniques are using larger number of semiconductor switches, those are requires lower-voltage systems and the small voltage steps must be supplied on the dc side either by a capacitor bank or isolated voltage sources.

4. Conclusion:

In this survey paper is reviewed, which is used to control the production of harmonics in the multilevel inverter of distribution energy system. For, a distributed generation system involving multiple energy sources and networks of different voltage levels, multilevel voltage source converters can effectively be used as a power management system. In recent the more commercial products are based on the multilevel inverter structure with worldwide research and development technologies. This paper cannot cover or reference all the related work, but the fundamental principle of different multilevel inverters has been introduced systematically. This discussed technology enable to achieve high efficiency, energy savings, improved performance, and compactness in almost all domestic, commercial, industrial and utility based applications.

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